

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps definitions from WL

Category	Themes (14)	Codes (42)	Study quotes the definition mentioning the code	Count	Subtotals
Organization, People, & Culture	Expansion to DevOps	expansion to DevOps	S1_IEEE_08, S1_SC_21	2	3
		extension to DevOps	S1_SC_01	1	
	Dev, Sec & Ops	development, operations and security teams	S1_IEEE_05, 08, 12, S1_SC_10, 21, S1_ACM_68	6	7
		dev/sec/ops	S1_IEEE_26	1	
	Culture	culture	S1_ACM_45	1	4
		cultural approach	S1_IEEE_26	1	
		cultural shifts	S1_ACM_50	1	
		shift the mindset	S1_IEEE_10	1	
	Collaboration	collaboration/collaborate	S1_IEEE_08, 12, 26, S1_SC_10, 21, S1_ACM_45, 68	7	7
	Breaking silos of security	breaking silos of security	S1_IEEE_08, 24, 26	3	4
		break down the barrier	S1_IEEE_22	1	
	Sharing knowledge	sharing that knowledge	S1_IEEE_08	1	3
giving that knowledge to the different teams		S1_IEEE_24, 26	2		
Process Capabilities	Integration of security into DevOps	incorporating security practices in the DevOps processes	S1_IEEE_08, S1_SC_21	2	14
		incorporation of security practices in a DevOps environment	S1_SC_10, 11	2	
		IT processes with security approach	S1_ACM_04, S1_IEEE_21	2	
		integration of security with development and operation	S1_SC_09	1	
		integrating security principles	S1_IEEE_12	1	
		integration of security processes and practices	S1_IEEE_10	1	
		introduction of more security-oriented processes	S1_SC_22	1	
		integrates continuous security into the original DevOps process	S1_IEEE_03	1	
		injection of security principles and controls into the DevOps	S1_ACM_50	1	
		integrating secure development best practices and methodologies into development and deployment processes	S1_IEEE_44	1	
		integrating the software development and operation processes considering security and compliance requirements	S1_SC_11	1	
	Agile	agile	S1_ACM_45, S1_IEEE_03	2	3
		smart and lightweight approach	S1_SC_31	1	
	Security is the main concern throughout the	security is the main emphasis	S1_SC_14	1	7
		security is given high priority throughout the SDLC	S1_ACM_07	1	
		a key concern throughout all phases of the	S1_SC_31	1	

	SDLC	development lifecycle and even post deployment			
		security practices are implemented at each stage of the cycle	S1_ACM_07	1	
		security is implemented at the right level and at right time	S1_IEEE_24	3	
	Shifting security to the start	puts security at the forefront of requirements	S1_IEEE_24	1	2
		shifting security to the early stages	S1_IEEE_06	1	
	Time reduction & Efficiency improvement	time reduction	S1_ACM_04, S1_IEEE_21	2	4
		increase deployment rates	S1_IEEE_22	1	
		increase the rate of testing feedback	S1_IEEE_22	1	
	Security assurance	maintaining a secure operational atmosphere	S1_IEEE_22	1	3
		identifying security vulnerabilities	S1_SC_31	1	
responsible for application security		S1_IEEE_05	1		
Technology	Reliance on operational tools	reliance on operational tools	S1_ACM_45	1	1
Business	Quality	without lost quality	S1_ACM_04, S1_IEEE_21	2	3
		quality affirmation	S1_SC_14	1	
	Authors of common definitions	Mohan & Othmane	S1_IEEE_08, 26, S1_SC_09, 10, 11, 21, 22, S1_ACM_45, 68	9	19
		Rahman & Williams	S1_IEEE_08, 12, 44, S1_SC_22	4	
		Carter	S1_IEEE_24, 26	2	
		Carturan & Goya	S1_ACM_04, S1_IEEE_21	2	
		Myrbakken & Colomo-Palacios	S1_IEEE_10	1	
		Mohan, Othmane, & Kres	S1_SC_11	1	

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps definitions from GL

Category	Themes (20)	Codes (35)	Study quotes the definition mentioning the code	Count	Subtotals
Organization, People, & Culture	Culture	culture	S1_GL_10, 13, 26	3	4
		cultural shift	S1_GL_11	1	
	Philosophy	philosophy	S1_GL_02, 19, 26	3	3
	Extension of the DevOps	extension of the DevOps	S1_GL_33	1	1
	Combination of DevOps and SecOps	combination of DevOps and SecOps	S1_GL_13	1	1
	Dev, Sec & Ops	development, operations, and security	S1_GL_15, 19, 27	3	3
	Collaboration	collaboration	S1_GL_26	1	2
		team work	S1_GL_02	1	
	Communication	communication	S1_GL_19	1	1
	Shared responsibility	shared responsibility	S1_GL_10, 33	2	6
everyone's responsibility		S1_GL_10	1		
security is a part of everyone's job		S1_GL_12	1		

		make everyone accountable for security	SI_GL_27	1	
		at the top of every developer's mind	SI_GL_12	1	
Process Capabilities	Integration of security into DevOps	integrating security methods into a DevOps process	SI_GL_02	1	6
		integrating security practices within the DevOps process	SI_GL_26	1	
		integration of security practices into a DevOps	SI_GL_10	1	
		adding security components to each step of the DevOps	SI_GL_23	1	
		bake security into the rapid-release cycles	SI_GL_11	1	
		integrating security into a continuous integration, continuous delivery, and continuous deployment pipeline	SI_GL_16	1	
	Agile	agile	SI_GL_05	1	1
	Emphasis on security	emphasizes the importance of sound information security practices	SI_GL_01	1	1
	Shifting security to the start	security from the start	SI_GL_04, 15	2	6
		from the beginning	SI_GL_33	1	
		integrate security objectives as early as possible	SI_GL_10	1	
		avoids any risk of security being an afterthought	SI_GL_01	1	
		placing security practices early during the SDLC	SI_GL_05	1	
Adoption of security through the entire SDLC	adoption of security through the entire SDLC	SI_GL_19	1	1	
Built-in security	built-in security	SI_GL_04	1	1	
Scalability	scalability	SI_GL_19	1	1	
Shorten the SDLC	shorten the SDLC	SI_GL_23	1	1	
Technology	Tooling	tooling	SI_GL_10	1	1
	Security-as-Code	security as code	SI_GL_26	1	1
	Automation	automation/automating	SI_GL_04, 19	2	2
Business	High software quality	high software quality	SI_GL_23	1	1

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps challenges from WL

Category	Themes (27)	Codes (50)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
Organization, People, & Culture	Resistance to change	developer resistance to integrate security protocol	S1_IEEE_08, S1_ACM_05	2	3
		developers lose autonomy	S1_IEEE_06	1	
	Challenges of collaboration, communication & coordination	teams working towards conflicting objectives	S1_SC_08	1	9
		insufficient monitoring of collaboration	S1_ACM_01	1	
		challenge of unrestricted collaboration	S1_IEEE_08, S1_ACM_05	2	
		coordination of security team and DevOps team	S1_IEEE_08, S1_ACM_05	2	
		un-trusted inputs causing isolation	S1_IEEE_08, S1_ACM_05	2	
		conflict between security and development	S1_IEEE_06	1	
	Neglecting security	management does not prioritize security	S1_IEEE_06	1	1
	Lack of security awareness and responsibility	improving security awareness	S1_IEEE_06	1	4
		nobody is responsible for security	S1_IEEE_06	1	
		security in the team and to the left	S1_IEEE_06	1	
		security push-pull	S1_IEEE_06	1	
	Lack of security knowledge and skills, need for training	lacking security education	S1_IEEE_06	1	3
lacking knowledge and training		S1_IEEE_06	1		
lack of knowledge		S1_IEEE_08	1		
Boundary between specialist & generalist	the boundary between a specialist and generalist	S1_IEEE_06	1	1	
Insufficient level of governance on DevSecOps adoption	insufficient level of governance on DevSecOps adoption	S1_SC_08	1	1	
Process Capabilities	Neglecting change control in security	neglecting change control in security	S1_IEEE_08	1	1
	Lacking security standards	lack of secure coding standards	S1_IEEE_08	1	1
	Difficulties in integrating security into DevOps without losing speed	difficulties in integrating security practices into a fast moving DevOps pipeline without slowing down the process	S1_SC_08	1	1
	Difficulties in transforming to DevSecOps without affecting current process	difficulties in running current product and services in parallel to its transformation to DevSecOps	S1_SC_08	1	1
	Ignoring processes and security essentials leading to technical and security debt	ignoring processes and security essentials leading to technical debt and security debt	S1_SC_08	1	1
	Lacking process and platform for communication, collaboration, and sharing	lack of common process and platform for communication, collaboration, and sharing information and feedback	S1_SC_08	1	1

	information and feedback				
	Out-of-sync domains and cross team dependencies causing issues in adopting DevSecOps	out-of-sync and conflicting domain specific bureaucratic processes for development, operation and security activities causing issues	SI_SC_08	1	1
	Using unsuitable metrics	using unsuitable performance metrics for security evaluation	SI_IEEE_08	1	3
		use of unsuitable metrics	SI_ACM_01	1	
		using unsuitable metrics	SI_ACM_05	1	
	Inconsistent security polices design	inconsistent security polices design	SI_ACM_05	1	2
		lacks with consistence security polices design	SI_IEEE_08	1	
	Compliance requirements	compliance requirements	SI_IEEE_07,SI_IEEE_08, SI_IEEE_11,SI_ACM_05	4	4
Tradeoff between security measures and CI system performance	the tradeoff between increased security measures, and the ability to access and modify the CI system as needed	SI_ACM_95	1	1	
Technology	Lack of tool standards	lack of tool standards	SI_IEEE_06	1	1
	Lack of mature tools for automation and security	lack of automated testing tools	SI_IEEE_06,SI_IEEE_08, SI_ACM_05	3	11
		lack of integrated testing tools to secure DevOps	SI_IEEE_08,SI_ACM_05	2	
		wrong automated deployment tools	SI_ACM_01, SI_IEEE_12	2	
		use of immature automated deployment tools	SI_ACM_01,SI_ACM_05, SI_IEEE_08,SI_IEEE_12	4	
	Challenges of legacy system refactoring	challenging to automate legacy system	SI_IEEE_06	1	1
	Threat modeling scalability issue	threat modeling scalability issue	SI_IEEE_08,SI_ACM_05	2	2
	Remaining manual security testing and need for automated testing performance measures	security manual testing	SI_IEEE_08,SI_ACM_05	2	4
		lack of automated testing performance measures for security	SI_IEEE_08,SI_ACM_05	2	
	Use of cloud and serverless computing brings security complications	move security to the cloud	SI_IEEE_06	1	17
		cloud security complications	SI_SC_25,44, SI_IEEE_16,25,39, SI_ACM_19,52,59.66	9	
		attacks due to miss-configured cloud environments	SI_IEEE_33,SI_IEEE_42	2	
		security smells in Infrastructure as Code (IaC)	SI_ACM_06,SI_IEEE_28, SI_SC_26	3	
invading VMs or containers		SI_ACM_52	1		

Business	Restructuring due to high cost and considering ROI (return on investment)	restructuring organization and implementing DevSecOps practices can lead to high cost such as salaries for security experts, costs on new tools	SI_IEEE_04	1	2
		risk and cost battle	SI_IEEE_06	1	
	Dilemma in selection of business processes for DevSecOps transformation	dilemma in selection of business processes in product and service delivery for transformation to DevSecOps	SI_SC_08	1	1
	Conflicting approaches to security and business requirements	security and business objectives are implemented using conflicting approaches	SI_ACM_64	1	1

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps challenges from GL

Category	Themes (16)	Codes (49)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
Organization, People, & Culture	Cultural resistance and organizational opposition	resistance to change	SI_GL_15	1	4
		challenge of the shifting role of security	SI_GL_37	1	
		organizational opposition	SI_GL_24	1	
		cultural resistance	SI_GL_20	1	
	Challenges of collaboration, communication & coordination	collaboration challenges	SI_GL_28,29	2	8
		failing to collaborate with the InfoSec team	SI_GL_18	1	
		lack of coordination between InfoSec team and developers	SI_GL_19	1	
		gaps between DevOps and Security teams	SI_GL_20	1	
		disconnect between security and development	SI_GL_39	1	
		friction between development and security teams	SI_GL_13	1	
		communication requirements	SI_GL_15	1	
	Urging velocity but neglecting security	developers are focused on velocity, not security	SI_GL_17	1	4
		DevOps teams neglect security	SI_GL_30	1	
		conflicting aims	SI_GL_38,40	2	
	Lack of security knowledge and skills, need for training	developers are not security specialists	SI_GL_15	1	6
		being unfamiliar with common security risks	SI_GL_18	1	
		the skills gap	SI_GL_37	1	
		not enough company stakeholders are security savvy	SI_GL_39	1	
		lack of security knowledge	SI_GL_38,40	2	
	Recruiting challenges	recruiting challenges	SI_GL_24	1	3
understaffing InfoSec teams		SI_GL_18	1		
engaging too late with the InfoSec team		SI_GL_18	1		
Process Capability	Fast changes and DevOps process conflict with slow security testing	rapid pace of change	SI_GL_29	1	6
		faster development process	SI_GL_28	1	
		security teams struggle to keep up with the	SI_GL_30	1	

		pace of DevOps			
		DevOps velocity	SI_GL_37	1	
		Slow security testing	SI_GL_38,40	2	
	Interconnectedness of the DevOps process	interconnectedness of the DevOps process	SI_GL_28	1	1
	Implementing security in CI/CD	implementing security in CI/CD	SI_GL_28	1	1
	Continuous deployment chaos	continuous deployment chaos	SI_GL_19	1	1
	Poor visibility of security track record	poor visibility of security track record	SI_GL_19	1	1
	Compliance at risks	compliance at risks	SI_GL_39	1	1
	Inadequate privileged credentials and access controls causing cyber attacks	inadequate controls provide an opening for attack	SI_GL_30	1	2
		privileged credentials used in DevOps are targeted by cyber attackers	SI_GL_17	1	
Technology	Lack of mature tools for automation and security	mismatched tools	SI_GL_15	1	4
		tool-centric approaches to secrets management create security gaps	SI_GL_17	1	
		inefficient Static AST tools (SAST)	SI_GL_19	1	
		manual pen-testing becomes a bottleneck	SI_GL_19	1	
	Legacy systems need for cloud support for scalability	lack of cloud support	SI_GL_19	1	3
		systems are not scalable	SI_GL_19	1	
		legacy infrastructure	SI_GL_24	1	
	Containers and other tools come with their own risks.	container and other tools can often be the reason for security concerns	SI_GL_20	1	3
		workload containerization	SI_GL_29	1	
		tools come with their own risks	SI_GL_30	1	
	Use of cloud and serverless computing brings security complications	security vulnerabilities in the Cloud	SI_GL_24	1	6
		server less computing	SI_GL_28	1	
		cloud security	SI_GL_29	1	
		cloud security complications	SI_GL_38,40	2	
		cloud and open source environments lead to compromise of critical information, configuration errors, compliance issues and security breaches	SI_GL_20	1	

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps practices from WL

Category	Themes (38)	Codes (76)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
Organization, People, & Culture	Collaboration	work collaboratively	SI_ACM_02	1	15
		enhanced collaboration	SI_ACM_02	1	
		cross-departmental collaboration	SI_IEEE_04	1	
		collaborating development, operation and security	SI_IEEE_04	1	
		increased collaboration between development, operations and security teams	SI_IEEE_12	1	
		close collaboration	SI_IEEE_12	1	
		collaboration within and between different teams	SI_IEEE_12	1	
		collaboration amongst different departments	SI_IEEE_12	1	
		collaboration between Dev&Ops	SI_IEEE_12	1	
		collaboration between Dev&Sec	SI_IEEE_12	1	
		collaboration between Sec&Ops	SI_IEEE_12	1	
		team collaboration	SI_IEEE_15	1	
		close collaboration of the teams	SI_IEEE_15	1	
		strong collaboration	SI_IEEE_15	1	
		collaboration between the security team and the development and operations teams	SI_IEEE_15	1	
	Communication	strong communication	SI_IEEE_15	1	8
		close communication	SI_ACM_02, SI_IEEE_09	2	
		good communication	SI_ACM_02	1	
		communication of security requirements	SI_ACM_02	1	
		virtual communication	SI_ACM_02	1	
		face-to-face communication	SI_ACM_02	1	
		physical communication	SI_ACM_02	1	
	Trust	trust	SI_ACM_02, SI_IEEE_29	2	7
trust worthy		SI_ACM_02	1		
trusted relationships		SI_ACM_02	1		
mutual trust		SI_ACM_02	1		
implicit trust		SI_ACM_02	1		
trust within the teams		SI_IEEE_29	1		
Security champions	security champions	SI_ACM_02	1	1	
Knowledge sharing	knowledge sharing	SI_ACM_02	1	1	
Shared responsibility for security	shared responsibility for security	SI_ACM_02	1	1	
Shameless retrospectives	shameless retrospectives	SI_IEEE_09	1	1	
Commitment & Agreement	commitment and agreement	SI_IEEE_29	1	1	
Enhance transparency	transparency	SI_IEEE_29	1	2	
	clear transparency	SI_SC_09	1		

	Feedback loop	feedback loops	SI_ACM_15	1	1
Process Capabilities	Shifting security to the left	shifting security to the left	SI_IEEE_04, 24, 26, SI_SC_08, 11, SI_ACM_50, 81	7	7
	Security-by-Design	security by design	SI_SC_07, 08, 18, 20, 22, SI_IEEE_16, 29, 30, 36, SI_ACM_45, 69	11	11
	Risk management	risk management (including risk assessment, risk treatment and risk control)	SI_SC_11, 18, 20, 22, 26, 40, 41, SI_ACM_03, SI_IEEE_34	9	9
	Compliance control	compliance control	SI_IEEE_11, SI_SC_27	2	2
	Continuous certification for DevOps	continuous certification for DevOps	SI_ACM_08	1	1
	Increase the visibility	increase the visibility	SI_SC_09	1	1
	Good documentation and logging	good documentation and logging	SI_IEEE_15	1	1
	Least privilege controls	least privilege controls	SI_IEEE_33	1	1
	Software process maturity	software process maturity - maturity models have emerged that let you link the degree of software security to the quality of the process	SI_SC_32	1	2
		Building Security In Maturity Model (BSIMM) model and The ISO/IEC 27035 Incident Management Cycle	SI_ACM_01	1	
MUSA security DevOps framework for multi-cloud applications	MUSA DevOps framework for security assurance in multi-cloud applications	SI_IEEE_16, SI_IEEE_40	2	3	
	MUSA Security DevOps (SecDevOps) framework	SI_ACM_52	1		
Technology	Automation	Automation	SI_ACM_01, 09, 49, 71, 72, 81, 95, SI_IEEE_06, 07, 09, 10, 12, 13, 15, 20, 21, 26, 38, 41, 54, 57, SI_SC_08, 09, 11, 17, 18, 20, 22, 26, 27, 32, 40	32	85
		Automated/automating test/testing	SI_ACM_01, 09, 49, 81, 95, SI_IEEE_06, 07, 09, 10, 12, 15, 21, 26, 38, 41, 54, 57, SI_SC_08, 09, 11, 17, 18, 22, 26, 27	25	
		Automated monitoring	SI_ACM_01, 71, 72, 81, SI_IEEE_07, 12, 13, 15, 21, 26, 38, SI_SC_08, 09, 18, 20, 26, 40	17	

		automated/automating/automatic deployment	SI_ACM_01, 09, 95, SI_IEEE_12, 15, 26, SI_SC_08	7	
		automated/automating scans	SI_IEEE_07, SI_SC_32	2	
		automated/automating code review	SI_IEEE_07, 12	2	
	Fault injection (chaos engineering)	Fault injection (chaos engineering)	SI_IEEE_13	1	1
	Security-as-Code	Security-as-Code	SI_SC_08, 09, 18, SI_IEEE_06,	4	4
	Continuous monitoring	Continuous monitoring	SI_IEEE_07, 12, 13, 15, 21, 26, 38, SI_SC_08, 09, 18, 20, 26, 40, SI_ACM_01, 15, 71, 72, 81	18	20
	Threat modeling	threat modeling/analysis	SI_IEEE_02, 04, 07, 11, 30, 36, 39, 61, 71, SI_SC_26	10	10
	Red team security drills	red team security drills	SI_IEEE_04	1	1
	Detect existing security flaws	detect existing security flaws	SI_SC_09	1	1
	Make sure the basics of host and network security are in place	make sure the basics of host and network security are in place	SI_SC_09	1	1
	Container security	Container/Containerization security	SI_ACM_52, SI_IEEE_55	2	9
		run container as non-root users	SI_SC_09, 34, SI_IEEE_55	3	
		use the latest version of image	SI_SC_42	1	
		conduct deep scanning of container image	SI_IEEE_04	1	
		enhance security of Docker	SI_IEEE_31	1	
		security practices in Kubernetes to manage containers safely	SI_IEEE_18	1	
	DAST	Dynamic Application Security Testing (DAST) techniques integrated into a CI/CD pipeline.	SI_IEEE_10	1	1
	RASP	Runtime Application Self-Protection (RASP) controls	SI_SC_32.	1	1
	Combination of static and dynamic analytical methods	A combination of static and dynamic analytical methods.	SI_IEEE_15	1	1
	Immutable-as-Code	Immutable-as-code can be used to ensure the immutability of infrastructure and avoid accidental configuration drifts	SI_IEEE_33	1	1
	Policy-as-Code	Policy-as-Code is an attempt to code the policy itself	SI_IEEE_33.	1	1
	Design-as-Code	Design-as-code: CAIRIS (Computer Aided Integration of Requirements and Information Security) model.	SI_IEEE_36	1	1

	Micro-segmentation	Micro-segmentation.	SI_SC_38.	1	1
	Advanced malware detection	Advanced malware detection - employs machine learning & deep learning	SI_SC_32	1	1
	Adopting DevSecOps in microservices-based applications	Adopting DevSecOps in microservices-based applications	SI_IEEE_17, 43, 52, 57, 84, 86, SI_SC_15, 36	8	8

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps practices from GL

Category	Themes (54)	Codes (106)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
Organization, People, & Culture	Cultural shift to security	cultural shift	SI_GL_41	1	2
		change the security mindset	SI_GL_32	1	
	Improving collaboration, communication & cooperation	cross-functional collaboration	SI_GL_30	1	7
		foster collaboration between security and development	SI_GL_25	1	
		open contribution and collaboration	SI_GL_24	1	
		collaboration and integration	SI_GL_02	1	
		communicate and collaborate	SI_GL_32	1	
		improving empathy and cooperation	SI_GL_10	1	
		reducing friction	SI_GL_10	1	
	Collective responsibility for security	collective responsibility	SI_GL_02	1	2
		assign security responsibility to one person from your DevOps team	SI_GL_28	1	
	Shared knowledge	learn from each other	SI_GL_32	1	2
		shared threat intelligence	SI_GL_24	1	
	Training, learning and education for security	provide training	SI_GL_06	1	6
		get training	SI_GL_10	1	
		enabling through training	SI_GL_32	1	
		cross-training	SI_GL_35	1	
		educate developers	SI_GL_25	1	
		security learning	SI_GL_14	1	
Recruiting success	recruiting success	SI_GL_10	1	2	
	invite InfoSec to demos	SI_GL_18	1		
Security champions	security champions	SI_GL_10	1	1	
Pragmatic implementation	pragmatic implementation	SI_GL_02	1	1	
Be reactive and responsive	be reactive and responsive	SI_GL_32	1	1	
Make security a priority	get buy-in from stakeholders	SI_GL_32	1	2	
	make security a priority	SI_GL_32	1		
Continuous feedback loop	continuous feedback loop	SI_GL_09, 13, 15, 22, 35	5	5	
Process Capabilities	Integrate security early	integrate security during the planning phase	SI_GL_35	1	3
		take a proactive approach to security	SI_GL_17	1	
		include security early in the life cycle	SI_GL_28	1	
	Secure-by-Design	secure by design	SI_GL_31	1	3

		embed security into each release	SI_GL_31	1	
		embedded security	SI_GL_19	1	
	Moving security to the left	moving security to the left	SI_GL_08, 09, 13, 15, 18, 31, 35, 36	8	8
	Define security requirements	define security requirements	SI_GL_06	1	2
		security requirements and design	SI_GL_14	1	
	Security reviews	conduct security reviews	SI_GL_18	1	2
		integrate security review into every phase	SI_GL_18	1	
	Security evaluation	security evaluation	SI_GL_14	1	2
		proactive security assessments	SI_GL_10	1	
	Enhance visibility	enhance visibility	SI_GL_41	1	1
	Better reporting	report	SI_GL_02	1	2
		better reporting	SI_GL_19	1	
	Measurement	define metrics	SI_GL_06, 19	2	3
		measurement	SI_GL_02	1	
	Policies	impose policy and governance	SI_GL_41	1	2
		implement security policies	SI_GL_30	1	
	Compliance	compliance	SI_GL_10	1	4
		compliance operations	SI_GL_24	1	
		identify compliance requirements beforehand	SI_GL_28	1	
		bridging the divide between compliance and development	SI_GL_02	1	
Vulnerability and incident management	vulnerability and incident management	SI_GL_14	1	5	
	Incident management	SI_GL_08, 10	2		
	vulnerability management	SI_GL_23, 30	2		
Privileged access management	privileged access management	SI_GL_30	1	2	
	secure access via secrets management	SI_GL_41	1		
Version control, metadata, and orchestration	version control, metadata, and orchestration	SI_GL_10	1	1	
Common weaknesses enumeration (CWE)	common weaknesses enumeration (CWE)	SI_GL_08	1	1	
Operational controls validation and improvement	operational controls validation and improvement	SI_GL_14	1	1	
Keep credentials safe	keep credentials safe	SI_GL_06	1	1	
Technology	Software Composition Analysis	software composition analysis and governance	SI_GL_06	1	2
		software composition analysis	SI_GL_23	1	
	Automation	automation	SI_GL_02, 04	2	15
		use tools and automation	SI_GL_06	1	
		automate protection of business logic flaws	SI_GL_19	1	
		automated code review	SI_GL_23	1	
		automate as much as possible	SI_GL_25, 28	2	
		automate tools and security processes	SI_GL_30	1	
		use automated security tools	SI_GL_41	1	

		automate security processes	SI_GL_17	1	
		automated security testing	SI_GL_08,11,13,15, 35	5	
	Threat modeling	threat modeling	SI_GL_06, 10, 14, 25, 28	5	5
	Continuous monitoring	continuous monitoring	SI_GL_06	1	5
		monitoring	SI_GL_02	1	
		24x7 proactive monitoring	SI_GL_24	1	
		monitor and scale	SI_GL_25	1	
		security monitoring	SI_GL_31	1	
	Secure coding	source code repository and scanning	SI_GL_10	1	6
		Secure coding	SI_GL_14	1	
		secure coding practice	SI_GL_10, 28	2	
		build preapproved code	SI_GL_18	1	
		conduct code dependency checks regularly	SI_GL_25	1	
	Sensitive information scan	sensitive information scan	SI_GL_23	1	1
	SAST	Static Application Security Testing (SAST)	SI_GL_02, 08, 23, 25	4	4
	DAST	Dynamic Application Security Testing (DAST)	SI_GL_02, 08, 23, 25	4	4
	IAST	Interactive Application Security Testing (IAST)	SI_GL_02, 08, 19, 25	4	4
	RASP	Runtime Application Self-Protection (RASP)	SI_GL_02, 08, 25	3	3
	Security-as-Code	Security-as-Code	SI_GL_32	1	1
	Compliance-as-Code	Compliance-as-Code	SI_GL_23	1	1
	Policy-as-Code	Policy-as-Code	SI_GL_17	1	1
	Consumable security services with APIs	Consumable security services with APIs	SI_GL_24	1	1
	Red and blue team exploit testing	red and blue team exploit testing	SI_GL_24	1	1
	Integrate security issues within your general bug tracker	Integrate security issues within your general bug tracker	SI_GL_19	1	1
	Configuration management	configuration management	SI_GL_10	1	1
	Host hardening	host hardening	SI_GL_10	1	1
	Application-level assessment	application-level assessment	SI_GL_10	1	1
CI/CD for patching	CI/CD for patching	SI_GL_10	1	1	
Container security	Docker security	SI_GL_10	1	4	
	Kubernetes security	SI_GL_10	1		
	Leverage containerization	SI_GL_28	1		
	Harden the container	SI_GL_41	1		
Verify cloud infrastructure	verify cloud infrastructure	SI_GL_28	1	1	
Business	Separation of duties	separation of duties	SI_GL_14, 17	2	2
	Business-driven security	business-driven security	SI_GL_24	1	1
	Availability and business continuity management	availability and business continuity management	SI_GL_14	1	1

	Linear scalability and affordable cost	linear scalability and affordable cost	S1_GL_19	1	1
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Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps metrics from WL

Category	Themes (6)	Codes (11)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
OPC	Security-trained rate	number of developers that have gone through security-training	SI_IEEE_06	1	1
Process Capabilities	Top vulnerability	number of mistakes in different security categories	SI_IEEE_06	1	2
		OWASP top 10	SI_IEEE_06	1	
Process Capabilities	Time spent correcting mistakes in each category	time spent correcting mistakes in each category	SI_IEEE_06	1	1
Technology	Penetration test pass rate	systems that are affected by internal and external penetration testing	SI_IEEE_06	1	1
	Security test pass rate	security test pass rate	SI_IEEE_57	1	3
		identify security vulnerabilities	SI_IEEE_57	1	
		ratio of failed-versus-pass static security source code scans	SI_IEEE_57	1	
	Code scanning detection rate	code scanning detection rate	SI_IEEE_57	1	3
		number of security scans identifies a problem in each timeframe or given process phase	SI_IEEE_57	1	
also include the number of problems		SI_IEEE_57	1		

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps metrics from GL

Category	Themes (6)	Codes (16)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
Process Capabilities	Top vulnerability	top vulnerability types and recurring bugs	SI_GL_43	1	1
	Security review performance	whether features undergo a security review	SI_GL_18	1	3
		whether security review slows down the development cycle	SI_GL_18	1	
		how well security is integrated into the delivery lifecycle	SI_GL_18	1	
	SLA performance	SLA performance	SI_GL_43	1	1
Critical risk profiling	critical risk profiling	SI_GL_43	1	1	
Technology	Whether automated testing covers security requirements	whether automated testing covers security requirements	SI_GL_18	1	1
	The use of preapproved libraries, packages, tool chains, and processes	use of preapproved libraries, packages, tool chains, and processes	SI_GL_18	1	1
	Using SAFe DevOps Health Radar	SAFe DevOps Health Radar measures DevOps performance, by assessing the maturity of four aspects and 16 activities of the CI/CD pipeline	SI_GL_01	1	1
	Number of adversaries per application	number of adversaries per application	SI_GL_43	1	1
	Adversary return rate	adversary return rate	SI_GL_43	1	1
	Defect density	defect density	SI_GL_43	1	1

	Defect bum rate	defect burn rate	S1_GL_43	1	1
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Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps tools from WL

Category	Themes (6)	Codes/Tools (14)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
Technology	Automation tools	Chef	S1_IEEE_07, S1_SC_12, 20, 26	4	10
		Jenkins	S1_SC_12	1	
		Ansible	S1_SC_20	1	
		Puppet	S1_SC_20	1	
		Gauntlt	S1_IEEE_06	1	
		SaltStack	S1_SC_01, 20	2	
	Automated code review tools	Veracode Greenlight	S1_SC_01	1	1
	Threat modeling tools	IriusRisk	S1_SC_01	1	2
		Microsoft threat modeling tool	S1_IEEE_39	1	
	Containerization tools	Docker	S1_SC_09, 18, 20, 29, 34, 42, 45, 48, S1_ACM_95, 99, S1_IEEE_31, 55	12	18
		Kubernetes	S1_ACM_52, 76, 89, S1_SC_20, 29, S1_IEEE_18	6	
Cloud security tools	Terraform	S1_SC_12, 20, S1_IEEE_33	3	3	
SAST tools	Kiuwan	S1_SC_01	1	1	
Advanced malware detection tool	CodeAI	S1_SC_01	1	1	

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps tools from GL

Category	Themes (14)	Codes/Tools (45)	Study mentions the code	Count	Subtotals
Technology	Automation tools	Ansible	S1_GL_04	1	1
	Containerization tools	Docker	S1_GL_03, 10	2	4
		Kubernetes	S1_GL_03, 10	2	
	Container security tools	Twistlock	S1_GL_42	1	3
		Notary	S1_GL_42	1	
		Aqua Security	S1_GL_42	1	
	Cloud security tools	AppScan on Cloud	S1_GL_42	1	4
		AWS Security service	S1_GL_42	1	
		ThreatModeler Cloud Edition	S1_GL_42	1	
		Trend Micro Cloud One	S1_GL_42	1	
	Automated code review tools	PMD	S1_GL_23	1	3
		DevSkim	S1_GL_23	1	
		FindSecBugs	S1_GL_23	1	
	Sensitive information scanning tools	TruffleHog	S1_GL_23	1	3
		GitSecrets	S1_GL_23	1	
		Talisman	S1_GL_23	1	
	SAST tools	Flawfinder	S1_GL_23	1	6
		Graudit	S1_GL_23	1	
		Bandit	S1_GL_23	1	
		Spotbugs	S1_GL_23	1	
SonarQube		S1_GL_23, 42	2		
DAST tools	OWASP ZAP	S1_GL_23	1	7	

		BDD Security	S1_GL_23	1	
		Arachini	S1_GL_23	1	
		Nikto	S1_GL_23	1	
		Radamsa	S1_GL_23	1	
		FuzzDB	S1_GL_23	1	
		Fortify Webinspect	S1_GL_42	1	
	RAST tools	Fortify Application Defender	S1_GL_42	1	1
	Software composition analysis tools	Retire.js	S1_GL_23	1	3
		OSSAudit	S1_GL_23	1	
		OWASP Dependency-Check	S1_GL_23	1	
	Compliance-as-code tools	nspec	S1_GL_23	1	3
		ServerSpec	S1_GL_23	1	
		OpenSCAP	S1_GL_23	1	
	Vulnerability management tools	Defect Dojo	S1_GL_23	1	8
		ArcherySec	S1_GL_23	1	
		Snyk	S1_GL_10, 21	2	
		HackerOne,	S1_GL_21	1	
		Claire	S1_GL_21	1	
		Stethoscope	S1_GL_21	1	
		Rapid7 Nexpose	S1_GL_21	1	
	Monitoring and alerting tools	Suricata	S1_GL_21	1	2
		NewRelic	S1_GL_42	1	
	DevOps performance measuring tool	SAFe DevOps Health Radar	S1_GL_01	1	1